

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 1 |
January 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Among All Other Biopsy for Suspected Pancreatic Cancer, How Efficient Is EUS-FNA and EUS-FNB. A Meta-Analysis

Stemy Kuttamparambil Simon^{1*}, Chao Liu¹, Yanxin He¹, Cunjing Fan^{1,2}, Xiaohui Gu¹

¹Department of General Surgery, Second Affiliated Hospital Of Zhengzhou University, China,

²Department of Ultrasonography, Second Affiliated Hospital Of Zhengzhou University, China

Accepted

January 27 ,2022

Published

January 31 ,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Chao Liu

None

*Corresponding Author:

Funding:

How to cite this article (APA): Stemy Kuttamparambil Simon, Chao Liu, Yanxin He, Cunjing Fan, Xiaohui Gu(2022). Among All Other Biopsy for Suspected Pancreatic Cancer, How Efficient Is EUS-FNA and EUS-FNB. A Meta-Analysis. *North American Academic Research*, 5(1), 78-89. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6213899>

ABSTRACT

Background: EUS guided tissue acquisition is the gold standard technique for sampling pancreatic masses. Even though EUS guided fine needle aspiration and fine needle biopsy are still under dispute.

Method: A computerized bibliographic search was conducted on main medical databases updated from 2017 to 2021 for including relevant RCTs in the Meta-analysis. The outcome measurements were diagnostic accuracy, specimen adequacy, adverse events, technical success (OR and 95%CI) and number of needle passes (MD and 95%CI).

Result: A total of 1167 cases were included in the study from 11 RCTs. Diagnostic accuracy (OR: 0.43, 95%CI: 0.30-0.61) and specimen adequacy (OR: 0.50, 95%CI: 0.33-0.76) is higher in FNB group compared to FNA group. Technical success and adverse events shows no significant difference between two groups. Number of needle passes to acquire adequate tissue sample is comparatively less in FNB group than in FNA group.

Conclusion: FNB is ideal choice over FNA for suspected pancreatic cancer masses.

Abbreviation: EUS-FNA = Endoscopic ultrasound guided fine needle aspiration, EUS-FNB = Endoscopic ultrasound guided fine needle biopsy, RCTs = Randomized control trials, OR = Odds ratio, CI = Confidence interval, MD = Mean difference.

Keywords

FNA, FNB, RCTs, Pancreatic masses

Introduction

Pancreatic cancer is a lethal and aggressive malignancy that has a very poor prognosis and high mortality rate. Based on GLOBOCAN 2018 the global cancer statistics shows the incidence and the mortality rate of

pancreatic cancer is approximately the same, which gives the pancreatic cancer the 7th most common cause of cancer related death(1). It is very difficult to accurately diagnose pancreatic cancer due to the late appearance of life threatening symptoms. At the time of initial diagnosis, majority of the cases are already metastasized. Hence, a swift and solid diagnostic technique is necessary in the medical field for Pancreatic cancer. At present EUS-FNA is the standard technique for diagnosing suspected pancreatic masses. The efficiency recorded as sensitivity from 85% to 95%, specificity from 95% to 98% and diagnostic accuracy from 78% to 95%(2,3). Despite the efficiency, FNA has some limitations. such as, by the absence of an experienced cytopathologist to perform ROSE (Rapid on-site evaluation) can have a negative impact on the diagnostic accuracy(4,5), most of the centers are unable to provide this evaluation. FNA provides Inadequate cytology specimen architecture to make a precise diagnosis(6).

Recently a new core biopsy needle has been introduced with reverse bevel sides and also with crown shaped tip for more advanced quality in diagnosis of the core specimen(7–9). There are quite a few Randomized control trials and Meta-analysis are conducted for comparing and find out the best option among EUS-FNA and EUS-FNB for diagnosing pancreatic cancer. Still this tissue acquisition method is controversial. Therefore, we performed a Meta-analysis from RCTs of FNA and FNB conducted in different countries for comparing the diagnostic accuracy and efficiency for sampling suspected pancreatic cancer.

Materials and methods

2.1. Search strategy

A computerized literature search was conducted on the main medical databases for RCTs that are updated from 2017 to 2020. The main search terms were EUS-FNA, EUS-FNB, Endoscopic ultrasound fine needle aspiration, Pancreatic, Pancreatic masses, Ultrasound guided fine needle tissue acquisition, Core biopsy. Additionally we searched records in Mesh-terms also, such as “Pancreatic Neoplasms”[Mesh], “Biopsy, Fine needle”[Mesh], (“Biopsy, Fine-Needle”[Mesh]) AND “Endoscopic Ultrasound-Guided Fine Needle Aspiration”[Mesh]. Only English articles are selected for the Meta-analysis.

Figure 1. Flowchart showing selection of studies.

2.2. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria: RCTs which provides the details of the patients who are above 18 years old who are suspected with pancreatic masses by CT (Computed tomography) MRI (Magnetic resonance imaging), or EUS. Records which are comparing EUS-FNA and EUS-FNB for tissue acquisition of pancreatic cancer tissue sampling under any of these outcome measures which are diagnostic accuracy, diagnostic adequacy, number of needle passes, adverse events and technical success.

Exclusion criteria: Review articles, Non RCTs, case reports, Records without full text and also without enough data are excluded.

2.3. Data extraction

One investigator extracted relevant information from the RCTs; that are name of the author, country, study duration, number of cases, type of needle and gauge, age of patients, tumor size, specimen prevention, follow-up of patients, ROSE (Rapid on-site evaluation), stylet and suction method during the trial, diagnostic accuracy, diagnostic adequacy, number of needle passes, adverse event, technical success.

For assessing the risk of bias Cochrane collaboration's tool was used with following several quality criteria: random sequence generation, allocation concealment, blinding of participants and personnel, blinding of outcome assessment, incomplete outcome data, selective reporting. Any disagreement in the data extraction were resolved through discussion with other two investigators.

2.4. Statistical analysis

All apposite data were inserted into Cochrane collaboration freeware software Review manager (RevMan 5.4) according to the general data type Dichotomous and Continuous; statistical method, analysis model, effect measure are varied.

For Dichotomous data, statistical method is Mantel-Haenszel with odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence interval (CI) is applied in fixed effect model. For Continuous data, statistical method is Inverse Variance with mean difference (MD) and 95% confidence interval (CI) is applied in random effect model. Chi-square test and I^2 statistic were used for the assessment of heterogeneity between studies. By funnel plot confirmed the absence of publication bias.

Result

3.1. Characteristics of selected studies

11 Randomized control trials are selected for the Meta-analysis, which includes 1167 cases for both EUS-FNA and EUS-FNB combined. In this 11 selected RCTs, 5 studies(10–14) are crossover and other 6 studies(15–20) are parallel. All characteristics of selected studies are described in Table 2. There are 11 studies used 22G and 3 studies used 25G aspiration needles from the manufacturer Cook medicals EchoTip needle (n=4), Boston Scientific Expect needle (n=5), Olympus EZ shot needle (n=3), Medtronic Beacon needle (n=2). Meanwhile, for biopsy needle 2 studies used 20G, 9 studies used 22G and other 2 studies used 25G from the manufacturer Cook medicals ProCore needle (n=9), Boston scientific Acquire needle (n=2), Medtronic SharkCore needle (n=2) .

Table 1.Kinds of FNA and FNB used in selected studies.

STUDY	COUNTRY	NEEDLE & GAUGE	MANUFACTURER
Lee BS, 2017	Korea	FNA 22G	EchoTip, Wilson-Cook medical, Winston-salem, NC, USA
		FNB 22G	EchoTip, ProCore, Wilson-Cook medical
Othman MO, 2017	USA	FNA 22G	EZ Shot 2, Olympus America Inc., Center Valley, PA
		FNA 22G	Expect, Boston Scientific Natick, MA
Bang JY, 2018	USA	FNB 22G	ProCore, Wilson-Cook medical, Winston-salem, NC, USA
		FNA 22G	Expect, Standard bevel, Boston scientific
Cheng B, 2018	China	FNB 22G	Acquire, Franseen biopsy, Boston scientific
		FNA 22G	EchoTip Ultra needle, Cook medical
Nagula S, 2018	USA	FNB 22G	EchoTip Procore needle, Cook medical
		FNA 22G	EchoTip, Cook medical, Bloomington, IN, USA
		FNA25G	Expect, Boston scientific, Natick, MA, USA
Noh DH, 2018	Korea	FNB 22G	ProCore, COOK-medical, Bloomington, IN, USA
		FNA22G	EZ Shot, Olympus, Japan
		FNB22G	EchoTip ProCore needle, Cook medical, Ireland
Tian L, 2018	China	FNA22G	Standard aspiration needle, Olympus
		FNB22G	Core biopsy needle, Cook EchoTip ProCore
vanRiet PA, 2019	Netherland	FNA25G	EchoTip Ultra, Cook-medical, Ireland
		FNB20G	ProCore, Cook-medical, Ireland
Oppong KW, 2020	United Kingdom	FNA22G	FNA needle, Beacon, Medtronic
		FNA25G	
		FNB22G	
Ardengh JC, 2021	Brazil	FNB25G	SharkCore FNB needle, Beacon, Medtronic
		FNA22G	Expect, Boston scientific, Marlborough, MA, USA
		FNB20G	ProCore, Cook-medical, Bloomington, IN, USA
Lee HW, 2021	Korea	FNA22G	Expect, Slimline, Boston Scientific, Natick MA, USA
		FNB22G	Acquire, Boston scientific, Natick, MA, USA

Five studies did rapid on-site evaluation (ROSE) during the trials. In vanRiet et al(19), among 13 EUS centers only 7 sites had conducted ROSE. Suction technique was used in 9 studies with 5ml, 10ml and 15ml syringes. 10ml syringe was most commonly used. Stylet was used in ten studies during the trial. In Cheng B et al(17), stylet was used only in first two needle passes. All studies had at least 6 months of follow-up for final diagnosis.

Table 2. Characteristics of selected studies.

Author	Country	Study Duration	No. of cases	Type of Needle & Gauge	Age	Tumor Size(cm)	ROSE	Specimen Preservation	Follow-up	Suction Tech	Stylet Use
Lee BS, 2017	Korea	2013-2014	7	22G FNA	69(26-85)	4.4±3.2	No	FFPE	12 Months	10ml Syringe	Yes
			9	22G FNB	66(36-81)	3.7±2					
Othman MO, 2017	USA	2013-2014	30	22G FNA	63.4±10	NR	Yes	Modified Camoy's Sol	≥6Months	10ml Syringe	Yes
			30	22G FNA	68.9±9.4						
Bang JY, 2018	USA	2016-2018	28	22G FNB	67.9±10.3	2.9±0.8	Yes	FFPE, Ethyl Alcohol	≥7Months	No	No
			46	22G FNA	67.9±14.7						
Cheng B, 2018	China	2014-2016	126	22G FNA	58.31±12.21	2.95	No	Formalin Fixed	≥48 Weeks	5ml Syringe	Yes
			123	22G FNB	58.34±11.1	2.91					
Nagula S, 2018	USA	2012-2014	83	22G & 25G FNA	66.5±13.0	3.30±1.66	Yes	Alcohol Solution, Standard Cytological Sol.	≥6Months	No	Yes
			93	22G & 25G FNB	66.5±13.0	3.51±2.38					
Noh DH, 2018	Korea	2013-2015	60	22G FNA	60.5±11.9	3.2±0.7	No	FFPE, 100% Ethanol	≥6Months	10ml Syringe	Yes
			60	22G FNB	62.6±7.7	3.0±1.0					
Tian L, 2018	China	2014-2015	18	22G FNA	61.4±6.9	2.17(1.2-3.6)	No	Cytolyt Solution, FFPE	≥6Months	5ml Syringe	Yes
			18	22G FNB	61.2±9.3	1.98(1.2-3.5)					
Van Riet, 2019	Netherland	2015-2016	158	25G FNA	66±0.7	2.7(2.0-4.0)	Yes	FFPE, Cytolyt Solution, Alcohol, CytoRich Red	≥9Months	Yes	Yes
			154	20G FNB		2.9(2.0-4.0)					
Oppong Kw, 2020	United Kingdom	2017-2018	22	22G FNA	69(30-87)	2.5(1.9-3.45)	Yes	CytoRich Red, FFPE	≥1Months	10ml Syringe	Yes
			33	25G FNB							
			21	22G FNB							
			32	25G FNA							
Ardengh Jc, 2021	Brazil	2017-2018	20	22G FNA	64.7±12.5	3.81±2.18	No	FFPE	≥6Months	10ml Syringe	Yes
			20	20G FNB							
Lee Hw, 2021	Korea	2017-2019	29	22G FNA	69.4±9.7	3.13±1.21	No	FFPE, Alcohol	≥9Months	5ml Syringe(2nd needle pass)	Yes
			27	22G FNB	67.6±10.1	3.14±1.03				10ml Syringe(3rd needle pass)	

FNA=Fine needle aspiration, FNB=Fine needle biopsy, G= Gauge, ROSE=Rapid onsite evaluation, FFPE=Formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissue preservation.

Figure 2. Forrest plot of diagnostic accuracy comparing FNA and FNB. FNA=Fine needle aspiration, FNB=Fine needle biopsy.

Figure 3. Forrest plot of specimen adequacy comparing FNA and FNB. FNA=Fine needle aspiration, FNB=Fine needle biopsy.

Figure 4. Forrest plot of number of needle passes comparing FNA and FNB. FNA=Fine needle aspiration, FNB=Fine needle biopsy.

Figure 5. Forrest plot showing the adverse event in both FNA and FNB groups. FNA=Fine needle aspiration, FNB=Fine needle biopsy.

Figure 6. Forrest plot for technical success in both FNA and FNB groups. FNA=Fine needle aspiration, FNB=Fine needle biopsy.

3.2 Diagnostic accuracy

Diagnostic accuracy was reported in 10 RCTs (Figure 2) Diagnostic accuracy is comparatively higher in FNB than FNA. (OR : 0.43, 95% CI : 0.30 - 0.61; I² = 39%) Fixed effect model was applied.

3.3 Specimen adequacy

Specimen adequacy was reported in 8 RCTs. (Figure 3) Specimen adequacy is higher in FNB group than in FNA group. (OR : 0.50, 95% CI : 0.33 – 0.76; I² = 1%) Fixed effect model was applied.

3.4 Number of needle passes

Number of needle passes was reported in 6 RCTs. (Figure 4) Number of needle passes is comparatively higher in FNA group than in FNB group. (MD : 0.09, 95%CI : -0.07 to 0.62; I² = 9%). Fixed effect was applied.

3.5 Adverse event

Adverse event was reported in 4 studies. (Figure 5) No heterogeneity in FNA and FNB groups. No significant difference shown. (OR : 1.56, 95% CI : 0.41 – 5.95; I2 = 0%).

3.6 Technical success

Technical success was reported in 8 studies. (Figure 6) No significant difference is spotted in both FNA and FNB groups. (OR : 0.76, 95%CI : 0.16 – 3.52; I2 = 0%).

3.7 Bias

Publication bias is detected by the funnel plot. Results from the figures 7,8 and 9 shows that the result of this study is symmetrical in main aspects. which indicates minimal publication bias.

Figure 7. Funnel plot on Diagnostic accuracy

Figure 8. Funnel plot on Specimen adequacy

Figure 9. Funnel plot on number of needle passes

Risk of bias summary and graph (Figure 10 & 11) depicts the overall risk across the study. All studies considered to have a high risk of performance bias due to the un-blinded character of the included RCTs. 3 studies (Nagula et al(11), Noh et al(12), Othman et al(16)) have high risk of reporting bias. Other 8 studies have low risk of reporting bias. All studies have low risk of selection bias, detection bias and attrition bias.

Figure 10. Risk of bias Graph

	Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)
Ardengh JC 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+
Bang JY 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+
Cheng B 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lee BS 2017	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lee HW 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+
Nagula S 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+
Noh DH 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+
Oppong KW 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+
Othman MO 2017	+	+	+	+	+	+
Tian L 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+
vanRiet PA 2019	+	+	+	+	+	+

Figure 11. Risk of bias summary

3.8 Discussion

For the past three decades EUS-FNA is the most preferred technique for sampling suspected pancreatic masses(21). But, there are few limitations that pulls FNA back in this most modern scientific world. EUS-FNA is limited in providing sufficient quantity of tissue for tumor marker assessment to personalize for early cancer treatment, aspirating cytological tissue instead of histological core tissue. It is always a risk to increase the number of needle passes which can lead different complications in the patients(22,23).

Furthermore, FNA is limited to provide better diagnostic accuracy without the presence of a cytopathologist who can render rapid onsite evaluation (ROSE), Which is not available in all EUS centers(24,25).

The newly designed FNB needle show exceptional result in sampling and diagnosing suspected pancreatic masses. In our Meta-analysis we found that, only FNB needle was superior in diagnostic accuracy and specimen adequacy with lower number of needle passes. Lower needle passes can avoid patients to encounter unnecessary adverse events like bleeding, abdominal pain or even pancreatitis after the technique. Adverse events and technical success have no difference in both FNA and FNB groups. In Nagula S et al(11) reported that in FNB and FNA after using ROSE shown same result, However in a recent randomized control trial(26) compared only FNB with and without using ROSE. FNB shows promising result without the support of ROSE. Also recently two Meta-analysis compared the efficiency of FNA and FNB. Antonio et al(27) reported that FNB clearly outperformed FNA by superior diagnostic accuracy (OR,4.10; 95% CI, 2.48-6.79; P<.0001) sample adequacy (OR,2.54; 95% CI, 1.29-5.01; P =.007) core tissue rate (OR,3.27; 95% CI, 2.03-5.27; P<.0001) low number of needle passes (MD -.75; 95%CI, -1.20 TO -.30; P=.001). In another Meta-analysis vanRiet et al(28) reported FNB shows higher diagnostic accuracy (87% vs 81%; P=0.02) higher tissue core rate (80% vs 62%; P=0.002) with lower number of needle passes (P=0.03). There are few limitations in our study must consider. We included very few RCTs in our study, we compared the diagnostic accuracy, specimen adequacy, number of needle passes, adverse events and technical success applied only in suspected pancreatic cancer masses. All randomized control trials have performance bias. In conclusion, we want our investigation helps the future researchers to decide the right choice of diagnostic technique for suspected sampling pancreatic cancer masses by taking this study as a reference in this modern medical scientific world.

References

1. Arnold M, Abnet CC, Neale RE, Vignat J, Giovannucci EL, McGlynn KA, et al. Global Burden of 5 Major Types of Gastrointestinal Cancer. *Gastroenterology*. 2020 Jul;159(1):335-349.e15.
2. Ngamruengphong S, Li F, Zhou Y, Chak A, Cooper GS, Das A. EUS and survival in patients with pancreatic cancer: a population-based study. *Gastrointest Endosc*. 2010 Jul;72(1):78–83, 83.e1-2.
3. Othman MO, Wallace MB. The role of endoscopic ultrasonography in the diagnosis and management of pancreatic cancer. *Gastroenterol Clin North Am*. 2012 Mar;41(1):179–88.
4. Siddiqui AA, Brown LJ, Hong S-KS, Draganova-Tacheva RA, Korenblit J, Loren DE, et al. Relationship of pancreatic mass size and diagnostic yield of endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine needle aspiration. *Dig Dis Sci*. 2011 Nov;56(11):3370–5.
5. Iglesias-Garcia J, Dominguez-Munoz JE, Abdulkader I, Larino-Noia J, Eugenyeva E, Lozano-Leon A, et al. Influence of on-site cytopathology evaluation on the diagnostic accuracy of endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine needle aspiration (EUS-FNA) of solid pancreatic masses. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2011 Sep;106(9):1705–10.
6. Levy MJ, Wiersema MJ. EUS-guided Trucut biopsy. *Gastrointest Endosc*. 2005 Sep;62(3):417–26.

7. Iglesias-Garcia J, Poley J-W, Larghi A, Giovannini M, Petrone MC, Abdulkader I, et al. Feasibility and yield of a new EUS histology needle: results from a multicenter, pooled, cohort study. *Gastrointest Endosc.* 2011 Jun;73(6):1189–96.
8. Larghi A, Iglesias-Garcia J, Poley J-W, Monges G, Petrone MC, Rindi G, et al. Feasibility and yield of a novel 22-gauge histology EUS needle in patients with pancreatic masses: a multicenter prospective cohort study. *Surg Endosc.* 2013 Oct;27(10):3733–8.
9. Bang JY, Hebert-Magee S, Hasan MK, Navaneethan U, Hawes R, Varadarajulu S. Endoscopic ultrasonography-guided biopsy using a Franseen needle design: Initial assessment. *Dig Endosc Off J Jpn Gastroenterol Endosc Soc.* 2017 May;29(3):338–46.
10. Bang JY, Hebert-Magee S, Navaneethan U, Hasan MK, Hawes R, Varadarajulu S. EUS-guided fine needle biopsy of pancreatic masses can yield true histology. *Gut.* 2018 Dec;67(12):2081–4.
11. Nagula S, Pourmand K, Aslanian H, Bucobo JC, Gonda TA, Gonzalez S, et al. Comparison of Endoscopic Ultrasound-Fine-Needle Aspiration and Endoscopic Ultrasound-Fine-Needle Biopsy for Solid Lesions in a Multicenter, Randomized Trial. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol Off Clin Pract J Am Gastroenterol Assoc.* 2018 Aug;16(8):1307-1313.e1.
12. Noh DH, Choi K, Gu S, Cho J, Jang K-T, Woo YS, et al. Comparison of 22-gauge standard fine needle versus core biopsy needle for endoscopic ultrasound-guided sampling of suspected pancreatic cancer: a randomized crossover trial. *Scand J Gastroenterol.* 2018 Jan;53(1):94–9.
13. Oppong KW, Bekkali NLH, Leeds JS, Johnson SJ, Nayar MK, Darné A, et al. Fork-tip needle biopsy versus fine-needle aspiration in endoscopic ultrasound-guided sampling of solid pancreatic masses: a randomized crossover study. *Endoscopy.* 2020 Jun;52(6):454–61.
14. Ardengh JC, Brunaldi VO, Brunaldi MO, Gaspar AF, Lopes-Júnior JR, Sankarankutty AK, et al. IS THE NEW PROCORE 20G DOUBLE FORWARD-BEVEL NEEDLE CAPABLE TO OBTAIN BETTER HISTOLOGICAL SAMPLES BY ENDOSCOPIC ULTRASOUND FOR DIAGNOSING SOLID PANCREATIC LESIONS? *Arq Bras Cir Dig ABCD Braz Arch Dig Surg.* 2021;33(4):e1554.
15. Lee BS, Cho C-M, Jung MK, Jang JS, Bae HI. Comparison of Histologic Core Portions Acquired from a Core Biopsy Needle and a Conventional Needle in Solid Mass Lesions: A Prospective Randomized Trial. *Gut Liver.* 2017 Jul 15;11(4):559–66.
16. Othman MO, Abdelfatah MM, Padilla O, Hussinat M, Elhanafi S, Eloliby M, et al. The cellularity yield of three different 22-gauge endoscopic ultrasound fine needle aspiration needles. *Diagn Cytopathol.* 2017 May;45(5):426–32.
17. Cheng B, Zhang Y, Chen Q, Sun B, Deng Z, Shan H, et al. Analysis of Fine-Needle Biopsy vs Fine-Needle Aspiration in Diagnosis of Pancreatic and Abdominal Masses: A Prospective, Multicenter, Randomized Controlled Trial. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol Off Clin Pract J Am Gastroenterol Assoc.* 2018 Aug;16(8):1314–21.
18. Tian L, Tang A-L, Zhang L, Liu X-W, Li J-B, Wang F, et al. Evaluation of 22G fine-needle aspiration (FNA) versus fine-needle biopsy (FNB) for endoscopic ultrasound-guided sampling of pancreatic lesions: a prospective comparison study. *Surg Endosc.* 2018 Aug;32(8):3533–9.
19. van Riet PA, Larghi A, Attili F, Rindi G, Nguyen NQ, Ruszkiewicz A, et al. A multicenter randomized trial comparing a 25-gauge EUS fine-needle aspiration device with a 20-gauge EUS fine-needle biopsy device. *Gastrointest Endosc.* 2019 Feb;89(2):329–39.

20. Lee HW, Kim KM. Randomized controlled trial comparing a conventional needle and a novel needle for endoscopic ultrasound (EUS)-guided histology of peripancreatic masses. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2021 Mar 12;100(10):e25106.
21. Yoshinaga S, Suzuki H, Oda I, Saito Y. Role of endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine needle aspiration (EUS-FNA) for diagnosis of solid pancreatic masses. *Dig Endosc Off J Jpn Gastroenterol Endosc Soc*. 2011 May;23 Suppl 1:29–33.
22. Chantrill LA, Nagrial AM, Watson C, Johns AL, Martyn-Smith M, Simpson S, et al. Precision Medicine for Advanced Pancreas Cancer: The Individualized Molecular Pancreatic Cancer Therapy (IMPACT) Trial. *Clin Cancer Res Off J Am Assoc Cancer Res*. 2015 May 1;21(9):2029–37.
23. Hashimoto S, Taguchi H, Higashi M, Hatanaka K, Fujita T, Iwaya H, et al. Diagnostic efficacy of liquid-based cytology for solid pancreatic lesion samples obtained with endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine-needle aspiration: Propensity score-matched analysis. *Dig Endosc Off J Jpn Gastroenterol Endosc Soc*. 2017 Jul;29(5):608–16.
24. Hébert-Magee S, Bae S, Varadarajulu S, Ramesh J, Frost AR, Eloubeidi MA, et al. The presence of a cytopathologist increases the diagnostic accuracy of endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine needle aspiration cytology for pancreatic adenocarcinoma: a meta-analysis. *Cytopathol Off J Br Soc Clin Cytol*. 2013 Jun;24(3):159–71.
25. Bang JY, Jhala N. Optimizing the diagnostic yield in endoscopic ultrasound-guided fine-needle aspiration: Is there an alternative to rapid onsite evaluation? *Dig Endosc Off J Jpn Gastroenterol Endosc Soc*. 2016 May;28(4):422–4.
26. Crinò SF, Di Mitri R, Nguyen NQ, Tarantino I, de Nucci G, Deprez PH, et al. Endoscopic Ultrasound-guided Fine-needle Biopsy With or Without Rapid On-site Evaluation for Diagnosis of Solid Pancreatic Lesions: A Randomized Controlled Non-Inferiority Trial. *Gastroenterology*. 2021 Sep;161(3):899-909.e5.
27. Facciorusso A, Sunny SP, Del Prete V, Antonino M, Muscatiello N. Comparison between fine-needle biopsy and fine-needle aspiration for EUS-guided sampling of subepithelial lesions: a meta-analysis. *Gastrointest Endosc*. 2020 Jan;91(1):14-22.e2.
28. van Riet PA, Erler NS, Bruno MJ, Cahen DL. Comparison of fine-needle aspiration and fine-needle biopsy devices for endoscopic ultrasound-guided sampling of solid lesions: a systemic review and meta-analysis. *Endoscopy*. 2021 Apr;53(4):411–23.

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

